

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' LINGUISTIC COMPETENCIES IN
"MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY" LESSONS OF THE 3rd GRADE

Tursunova Zarina Ne'matovna

Teacher of Asian International University

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' LINGUISTIC COMPETENCES IN THE 3ND
GRADE "MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY" CLASSES

Abstract: In this article, students of the 3rd^{grade} in the lessons of "Mother language and reading literacy" correctly pronounce speech sounds, describe different events in their speech, move syllables, head playing of letters, asking questions and similar grammatical concepts from practice. Studies as theoretical knowledge, as well as comments on the formation of speech competencies.

Key words: National curriculum, listening comprehension, linguistic competence, playing .

Uzbekistan Republic President of Uzbekistan new development during education and fields of science development measures on " (PF - No. 6108 06.11.2020.) as scheduled , by March 1 , 2021 until qualified pedagogue , scientific staff , psychologist and foreign experts (this including Finland qualified involve specialists). did without National study program work will be released . In this process support general education institutions is determined and 2021-2022 - academic in the year education in the process this program experiment as current will be done .

This is it program now current done , his from the previous ones different aspects the following :

1. The former study programs content is 90% theory consists of being teaching methodology to memorize directed . new National study program content is 50% theory , 50% practice consists of will be and of the student independent activities to support is directed .
2. Study in programs evaluation while only remembering the rest knowledge size determined . new program based on in students formed skills is evaluated .
3. Sciences the number and study downloads optimized for readers interest according to sciences choose reading enable giver variant study programs based on to life and professional to the activity preparation opportunity is created .
4. National study program based on sciences linear in order not spiral way is taught . That is topics repeated not each other logically continue bringer and simply complex towards directed way is entered .

To the reader the language teaching through that's it language according to possessed speech of activity main four type : **speech listening understand , speak , read and to write** deeds according to each one in class requirement to be done qualification and skills the norm development , in this reading and work in the process , family and public in places surface coming different speech situations independent respectively thought exchange get and thought be able to tell , heard the material perception also in writing sources reading through information get , to events own attitude notice in the style of to communicate access qualification take over to go dynamics mean is caught . " Mother language " not only lexicon and grammar standards teacher , perhaps student speech in the activity optional subject , sciences in the section texts

listening understand , right reading , orthoepic and orthographic standards apply potential development service who does is a science . The student's logical , critical , creative thinking for mother language in their classes by reading to understand separately attention is directed . Mother language thorough mastered student another sciences satisfactory absorbs .

Primary education system improving students independent the thinker person as vital to processes prepared to go issue own the future and society development for who can feel responsible perfect generation adult deliver purpose in itself expression is enough This point of view meaning , today in the day education in the content importance more and more increased the growing concept of " competence " . in particular to stop permissible Because next in years language to education communicative approach , integrar approach , competence approach such as new approaches app is being done .

Competence is either this field according to is knowledge . Competence (lat. " compete " - I am achieving , I am worthy , I am worthy) - in science occupied theoretical knowledge , practical skill and qualifications diary in life face coming practical and theoretical issues in solving using , in practice apply is to get [3].

Competence of the concept education to the content app to be done at the core teaching to the system relatively new approach , education system development issue lies , of course . Current time on demand monad way now to the students only scientific and theoretical knowledge to give with satisfied without staying , maybe of children worldview expand them independent able to observe , possessed knowledge diary conscious of life respectively app do it will receive person as formation " competence " and " competence " concepts each one of the lesson main purpose to the content to absorb accent be given started

Competence is expected to the result take coming activity is a sign . It is knowledge product is an expert by him in practice apply get is the ability . of competence from knowledge difference that is , the task practical without performing standing up , him cannot be determined or evaluated . Qualification of competence important criterion it is different in cases , that's it row problematic the same in situations how many there is apply as a result manifestation will be [5].

Modern approaches teaching in the process pedagogical and information technologies mutually integration through in students support and to science about private competencies to form mean holds It is known that the students formable competencies two type separated : support and to science about competencies . Some in sources while The following 3 types of competencies are classified:

1. core competencies;
2. general (subject) competencies;
3. private competencies.

Competencies that prepare the ground for the general development of a student's personality *are basic competencies* , competencies that are formed only through the subject of study. *private competencies* is called

Students speech competencies formed the following criteria through manifestation will be :

- teacher speech , video and audio texts (multimedia applications) and assignments listening understand takes

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- pictures based on and by reading broadcasted text on the surface to the conversation enter takes , speech in the process mastered new the words oral in speech apply takes
- exercise in the text the words adding read takes , to the tone of speech compliance did without smooth and expressive read takes , letters compound participation reached the words read takes
- in the word how many sound if so , that's it joint to be , one vowel sound joint harvest to do , i.e. o- na , u- ka , a- ka such as to the joint be takes , letters compounds participation reached the words to the joint be takes
- x and h sound the words right write takes
- one topic within to questions answer write takes
- torch , approval , education , courage , bow such as catch up certain the words to the joint being write takes
- vocabulary , explanatory , hearing , by heart written , pictorial dictation write takes and the sentences pictures in order copy it takes

To competence never when straight away diagnosis to put and evaluation possible not but each always his efficiency point of view in terms of indirectly understanding can Modern in education to competence based on approach - taken knowledge apply ability attention focus is a method .

CONCLUSION

Development of the country of young people in the future how person being maturity to find organic depends . Our children the future foundation to be initial education system more reform to do while this about priority from tasks one is considered As you know , general medium education schools undertake education process through in students support competencies , including communicative , information with work get , person as himself development , social active civil , general , mathematical literacy , science and technique news informed to be and use competencies formation task loaded . This process done in raising first of all teacher his own take over standing position level professional to competence have to be it is necessary Only then is he a pedagogue the process successful can organize . Already him professional knowledge , honesty , truthfulness , inquisitiveness , tireless prolific work , creativity and creativity such as qualities raises . Like this qualities through pedagogue high spiritual , deep to the idea have mature individuals maturity find no doubt .

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